

Synthesis and Screening of Some 1,3-Propane Diones and Flavones

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Variously substituted 1,3-propane diones and flavones are synthesised. Structures of the compounds are established by chemical and spectral data. The compounds are tested for antifungal and antibacterial activities.

FLAVONES are known to play a vital role in plant life¹⁻⁴. Many synthetic flavones are known to possess various physiological activities⁵⁻¹³. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to synthesise some new members of this series and test them for their biological activity.

A majority of the naturally occurring flavones have mainly hydroxy and methoxy groups as substituents either in the benzenoid ring or at three position. In the present work, flavones having methoxy and methyl substituents in the 2-phenyl ring and methyl and halogeno substituents in the benzenoid part have been synthesised.

Synthesis of the title compounds was accomplished through three steps. The first step involved the esterification of variously substituted *o*-hydroxy acetophenones with methoxy and methyl substituted benzoic acids¹⁴. Structures of these compounds (I) were confirmed by their insolubility in aqueous NaOH solution and ir spectral data.

IR (nujol) showed bands at 1720 cm⁻¹ (C=O ester), 1358 cm⁻¹ (CH₃ symmetrical stretch),

1190 cm⁻¹ (O=C-C stretch). Physical data of these compounds are given in Table 1.

These esters (I) were subjected to Baker-Venkataraman transformation¹⁵⁻¹⁷ using pyridine and potassium hydroxide, when the corresponding 3-(*o*-hydroxy substituted phenyl)-1-(substituted phenyl)-propane-1,3-diones (II) were obtained.

IR (nujol) of these compounds showed bands at 1550 cm⁻¹ (C=O enolic) and 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=O, conjugated).

Physical data of these compounds are recorded in Table 2.

These 1,3-propane diones (II) were cyclised to the corresponding flavones (III) by refluxing them in acetic acid-hydrochloric acid mixture.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED-2-(2'-BENZOYLOXY)-ACETOPHENONES (I)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R'	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	85
2.	H	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	87
3.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	102
4.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-OH	70
5.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-OH	87
6.	H	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	95
7.	H	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	80
8.	H	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	85
9.	H	H	Cl	2'-OH	70
10.	H	H	Cl	4'-OH	88
11.	H	H	Br	2'-OCH ₃	78
12.	H	H	Br	3'-OCH ₃	78
13.	H	H	Br	4'-OCH ₃	90
14.	H	H	Br	2'-OH	62
15.	H	H	Br	4'-OH	101
16.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	94
17.	CH ₃	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	95
18.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	105
19.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-OH	100
20.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-OH	120
21.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	77
22.	H	CH ₃	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	62
23.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	91
24.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-OH	62
25.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-OH	95
26.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	101
27.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	98
28.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	98
29.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-OH	78
30.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-OH	75
31.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	65
32.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	65
33.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	105
34.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-OH	84
35.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-OH	100
36.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	108
37.	Cl	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	84
38.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	107
39.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-OH	110
40.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-OH	90

Solvents for crystallisation : Aqueous alcohol for Sl. Nos. 3-6, 17, 22, 30, 32, 36 and alcohol for the rest.

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TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED 1,3-PROPANEDIONES (II)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R'	Yield %	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	72	110
2.	H	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	76	107
3.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	69	128
4.	H	H	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	80	85
5.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	82	120
6.	H	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	79	140
7.	H	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	68	112
8.	H	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	78	120
9.	H	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	72	105
10.	H	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	77	108
11.	H	H	Br	2'-OCH ₃	65	138
12.	H	H	Br	3'-OCH ₃	70	114
13.	H	H	Br	4'-OCH ₃	72	128
14.	H	H	Br	2'-CH ₃	69	85
15.	H	H	Br	4'-CH ₃	76	115
16.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	68	123
17.	CH ₃	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	65	103
18.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	70	96
19.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	75	110
20.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	80	118
21.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	82	133
22.	H	CH ₃	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	88	167
23.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	79	150
24.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-CH ₃	76	100
25.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-CH ₃	80	142
26.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	82	108
27.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	84	90
28.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	69	140
29.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	74	110
30.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	76	118
31.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	76	132
32.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	69	95
33.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	78	145
34.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	59	82
35.	H	OH	OH	4'-OH	65	120
36.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	80	153
37.	Cl	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	82	140
38.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	79	148
39.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	81	95
40.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	70	114

All the compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

Solvents for crystallisation : Alcohol + AcOH for Sl. Nos. 11, 13, 16; AcOH for 88 and alcohol for the rest.

IR (nujol) of these compounds showed bands at 1610-40 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1550 cm⁻¹ (C=C) and

1350 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C).

NMR (CCl₄) of (a) 6-methyl-2-(2'-tolyl)-chromone and (b) 6,7-dimethyl-2-(2'-tolyl)-chromone showed following signals :

(a) 2.5 (s, 6H, 6-CH₃ and 2'-CH₃); 6.3 (s, 1H, 3-H); 8.0 (s, 1H, 5-H) and 7.1-7.83 (m, 6H, aromatic).

(b) 2.3 (s, 6H, 6-CH₃ and 2'-CH₃); 2.53 (s, 3H, 7-CH₃); 6.17 (s, 1H, 3-H); 7.8 (s, 1H, 5-H) and 7.1-7.83 (m, 5H, aromatic).

Physical data of the flavones are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF SUBSTITUTED FLAVONES (III)

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R'	Yield %	m.p. °C
1.	H	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	78	128
2.	H	H	OH	2'-CH ₃	82	133
3.	H	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	79	151
4.	H	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	85	199
5.	H	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	87	145
6.	H	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	90	134
7.	H	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	88	196
8.	H	H	Br	2'-OCH ₃	76	207
9.	H	H	Br	3'-OCH ₃	80	162
10.	H	H	Br	2'-CH ₃	79	115
11.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-OCH ₃	88	159
12.	CH ₃	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	86	180
13.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	90	191
14.	OH	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	91	148
15.	OH	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	79	185
16.	H	CH ₃	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	76	180
17.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-OCH ₃	81	227
18.	H	CH ₃	Cl	2'-CH ₃	80	150
19.	H	CH ₃	Cl	4'-CH ₃	83	175
20.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	85	145
21.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	88	156
22.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	90	174
23.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	79	120
24.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	85	177
25.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-OCH ₃	82	188
26.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	3'-OCH ₃	88	155
27.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-OCH ₃	90	183
28.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	2'-CH ₃	89	120
29.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	4'-CH ₃	91	156
30.	Cl	H	Cl	3'-OCH ₃	76	188
31.	Cl	H	Cl	2'-CH ₃	84	125
32.	Cl	H	Cl	4'-CH ₃	86	174
33.	H	H	Br	2'-Cl	90	162
34.	H	H	Br	4'-Cl	88	225
35.	CH ₃	H	Cl	2'-Cl	92	157
36.	CH ₃	H	Cl	4'-Cl	90	238

All the compounds gave satisfactory C and H analysis.

Solvents for crystallisation : Alcohol + AcOH for Sl. Nos. 4, 12, 13, 16, 17, 25, 30; AcOH for Sl. Nos. 34-36 and alcohol for the rest.

Experimental

Synthesis of substituted-2-(substituted benzoyloxy)-acetophenones (I) : A mixture of substituted *o*-hydroxy acetophenone (0.04 mole) and substituted benzoic acid (0.05 mole) was dissolved in pyridine (20 ml). This solution was ice cooled and phosphorous oxychloride (5 ml) was added slowly with

stirring. The reaction mixture was kept at room temp. for 2 hr and poured on ice and dil. HCl. The solid thus obtained was washed successively with water and 2% NaOH solution, filtered and crystallised from a proper solvent.

Synthesis of 3-(*o*-hydroxy substituted phenyl)-1-(substituted phenyl)-propane-1,3 diones (II) : A mixture of the ester (I) (0.01 mole), dry pyridine (20 ml) and powdered potassium hydroxide (0.04 mole) was stirred for about 20 min and allowed to stand for ~0.5 hr. The reaction mixture was acidified with dil. HCl when a yellow product precipitated out. It was filtered and crystallised from a proper solvent.

Synthesis of substituted flavones (III) : A mixture of 3-(*o*-hydroxy substituted phenyl)-1-(substituted phenyl)-propane-1,3 dione (II) (1 g), glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and conc. HCl (2 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured over crushed ice when the corresponding flavones (III) were obtained as white solid. They were crystallised from a proper solvent.

Biological activity :

Some β -diketones (II) and flavones (III) synthesised in this work were screened for antifungal and antibacterial activity.

Aspergillus flavus (an aflatoxin producing fungus) was used for antifungal screening. The compounds were tested at 100 ppm by paper disc method and activity was measured in terms of zone of growth inhibition in mm.

Some of the β -diketones [Table 2 (Sl. Nos. 1, 2, 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 18, 20, 33, 36 and 38)] showed moderate activity (zone of inhibition 6-8 mm).

The flavones [Table 3 (Sl. Nos. 1, 2, 3, 10, 12, 20, 21, 22, 23, 28, 35 and 36)] showed moderate activity.

Antibacterial activity was evaluated by testing the compounds against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Serratia marcescens* and *Rhizobium* sp. None of the compounds showed any appreciable activity.

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